

mosaic

MOSAIC Mutual Learning Programme

Deliverable No. 5.2

ERRIN
31/12/2021

Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101006382 - H2020-SwafS-2018-2020 / H2020-SwafS-2020-1

Executive Summary

This document looks to set out the main characteristics of the peer learning programme within the MOSAIC project. At its inception, the Community of Practice (CoP) was designed to work with two front runner cities, Brussels and Milan, who would be leading the way in bring their cities to climate neutrality by 2030. Throughout the course of the first year of the project, it was decided to rather involve a bigger number of cities from an early stage of the co-design and co-creation pilots, to better be in line with recent developments regarding the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Mission.

The Mission has been officially launched in November 2021, with the Expression of Interest for cities to apply for the Mission being open from end of November until end of January 2022. In order for MOSAIC not to be limited to the two originally planned cities, the Consortium published on 8 November 2021 an open call for more cities/regions to express interest in working with us (with deadline on November 24, 2021). 17 cities expressed such interest. While Brussels has not expressed any interest to be involved, Milan has confirmed its involvement. Originally planned co-design and co-creation activities will thus involve a broader number of cities and take the shape of webinars and training opportunities on citizen engagement in open innovation settings, and tailored support on how to address and boost multi-stakeholder engagement in their application to the Mission Expression of Interest.

MOSAIC Community of Practice is therefore be composed of at least the 17 European cities who have expressed interest to collaborate. The planning of mutual learning is a work in progress – steps taken so far are described in this deliverable.

Deliverable Information

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CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>
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R	Report	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
D	Demonstrator	<input type="checkbox"/>
W	Website, patent filing, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>

O	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>
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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long Form
EC	European Commission
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
CCC	Climate City Contract

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Introduction

MOSAIC aims to study, prove and assess how solutions to societal challenges, such as leading cities towards climate neutrality, can be enhanced by actively involving all concerned stakeholders through sound methodological approaches. In particular, MOSAIC focuses on exploring the role and engagement of citizens in a process of co-innovation, where all actors are fairly rewarded.

With this in mind, this task and subsequent deliverable aims to deepen the MOSAIC project's stakeholder base by identifying "mirror ecosystems", cities or metropolitan areas from across the European Union, with a specific interest in discussing and replicating the MOSAIC methodology in their local environment and building a vibrant community of quadruple helix representatives. These "mirror ecosystems" will subsequently be referred to as "cities".

During the proposals phase, the MOSAIC project had planned to recruit four cities to work with the pilots taking place in Milan and Brussels, however, due to the way the **Cities Mission** developed, as detailed below, the decision was taken to expand the call and invite all interested cities from across the EU to form a **Community of Practice (CoP)**.

This document will first outline the current state of play of the Cities Mission, highlighting the links and impact on the operationalisation of the MOSAIC Community of Practice. Subsequently, the document will go on to set out a first framework for the future 'Mutual Learning Programme'. This programme will not only share the research conducted in the other work packages but also capitalise on the extensive experience of the MOSAIC consortium to support cities in understanding the value of citizen engagement in co-innovation to achieve climate neutrality objectives.

This document, similarly to the Community of Practice, will continue to evolve as both the MOSAIC project and the Cities Mission develop. Therefore, this first iteration will look to set out a number of KPIs, but also allow enough flexibility for the MOSAIC project to effectively support the selected cities on their journey to climate neutrality through multi-stakeholder engagement.

At the end of the project, the final iteration of this deliverable should act as a roadmap for successfully sharing knowledge, exchange good practices and operationalise academic research with cities that are focused on tackling the pressing societal and global challenges of today.

EU Mission: 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities (Cities Mission)

Due to the close interconnection of the MOSAIC Project and the Cities Mission, the following section of this document will set out the current state of play of the Cities Mission, with a particular focus on expectations towards cities and plans for stakeholder and citizen engagement.

On 25 November 2021, the European Commission (EC) launched a call for expressions of interest for cities to join the European Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities.

The objectives of the mission are to achieve 100 climate-neutral and smart European cities by 2030 and to ensure that these cities act as experimentation and innovation hubs to enable all European cities to follow suit by 2050.

Joining the mission will put the selected cities right at the innovation forefront of the transition towards climate neutrality, as part of the European Green Deal. As the fight against climate change increasingly turns to deployment of solutions, cities are best placed to be the early adopters of the policies to achieve climate neutrality. In the process, it will allow them to deliver a wide range of benefits to their communities and citizens, including reduced air and noise pollution, less congestion, lower energy bills and healthier lifestyles.

Benefits for Cities

Cities participating in the mission will prepare and implement a “Climate City Contract” that will be co-created with **local stakeholders** and **citizens**. The benefits that the Cities Mission will offer to participating cities include:

- Tailor-made advice and assistance from a “Mission Platform” for example towards developing an Investment Plan to draw in external finance;
- Unlocking additional funding and financing opportunities through a “Mission label”;
- Funding opportunities for cities to be part of large innovation actions, pilot projects and demonstrators;
- Support through a national coordination network;
- Networking opportunities, learning and exchange of experiences among cities
- Buy-in and **involvement of citizens** and **local communities** for climate neutral solutions
- High visibility – raising political profile and attractiveness for investment and skilled workers.

In October 2021, the European Commission has published an [Info Kit](#) for cities and a list of [Frequently Asked Questions](#) that contained detailed information about the selection process, the functioning of the mission and, importantly, what concretely will be expected of cities that decide to become part of this Mission.

Next Steps for the Cities

Cities have been invited to express their interest in becoming climate-neutral by 2030 as part of the Mission and to submit information about their current situation, ongoing work and future plans as regards climate neutrality.

Cities can register for the call for [expression of interest](#). The call will remain open until 31 January 2022, after which it will be assessed by independent experts and the European Commission will announce the list of selected participant cities by April 2022. The first cities will be able to start working on their Climate City Contracts with the support of the Mission Platform as soon as the selection process is completed.

Figure 1 – Timeline for the EU Mission for 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities

MOSAIC & the Cities Mission

MOSAIC will address this SwafS knowledge base gap, exploring how to translate the involvement of stakeholders “from all parts of the quadruple helix”, typical of SwafS and RRI, in Open Innovation ecosystems, within the context of a mission-like environment focused on climate neutral and smart cities priorities.

Drawing upon the richness of SwafS experiences so far, MOSAIC’s research will lead to the assessment of effective instruments applicable to successful co-creation approaches in quadruple-helix Open Innovation pathways. While doing so, the MOSAIC consortium will define and assess indicators to measure impact and transformative changes that are specific to this particular context, generating scientific publications as well as toolkits to be further used both within future SwafS-like initiatives and beyond.

Initially, the MOSAIC project planned to engage with two pilot actions in the cities of Brussels and Milan, to test MOSAIC’s methodological approach and research actions, specifically those developed in Work Package 4. The piloting process has been designed to produce concrete instruments and recommendations for these two pilot cities in their Mission journey. In addition, the results of these pilots were expected to be replicated in four European cities that had also show interested in joining the Cities Mission.

A Joined-Up Approach

As the Cities Mission was launched in October 2021, along with the large-scale European Green Deal project [NetZeroCities](#) - which has been designed to support the operationalisation of the Cities Mission – it has been important to reflect on the assumptions made at a stage when less information on the Cities Mission was available. As a result of this reflection process, the MOSAIC consortium has been quick to adapt and realign its proposed activities with the implementation plan of the Cities Mission.

As soon as the call for expressions of interest was launched by the European Commission in November 2021, the MOSAIC consortium proposed an updated approach to better utilise the research potential of the project and increase the impact on cities looking to be part of the Cities Mission. In their application to be part of the Mission, cities will be strongly encouraged to carefully consider and outline their citizen engagement initiatives, in particular through co-design and co-creation approaches. Whether they are a frontrunner city, already advanced on their Climate City Contract, or taking the first steps into the Mission, MOSAIC will provide unique expertise and a robust methodology to support citizen engagement approaches tailored to this specific mission context.

As laid out in Figure 2 below, the MOSAIC consortium devised a four-step programme to increasing the project’s impact on cities and providing tailored support to them during the expression of interest phase to ensure that citizen engagement is reflected in their applications.

In December 2021, the MOSAIC project launched its own call for expressions of interest, which was aimed at selecting a group of cities for collaboration, subsequently constituting the MOSAIC Community of Practice. This group of cities will be supported in their citizen engagement activities within the context of their involvement in the Horizon Europe Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Mission. More information on this call can be found in the section **Error! Reference source not found.**

Developing the **MOSAIC** Community of Practice

Figure 2 - Developing the MOSAIC Community of Practice

In the short time that the Cities Mission Expression of Interest is open, the MOSAIC partner aim to support all those cities that apply to be a part of the Community of Practice with general and tailored services. An initial webinar introducing the importance of citizen and multi-stakeholder engagement took place in December 2021 and will be followed up by bespoke one-on-one meetings with each city in January 2021. More information on this call can be found in the section **Error! Reference source not found.**

In addition, ERRIN will continue to use its position in the NetZeroCities project, to provide a feedback loop with the Citizen Engagement aspects of the NetZeroCities and the outcomes and findings from within the MOSAIC Community of Practice. An introductory meeting has already taken place between Stickydot, ERRIN, FGB and Democratic Society at the end of 2021.

The MOSAIC Expression of Interest

As mentioned in the previous section, the MOSAIC partners launched an expression of interest for cities to join its Community of Practice in October 2021. Through this Community of Practice, the MOSAIC partners aim to study, prove and assess how co-creation practices involving all actors of the quadruple helix (academia, industry, government, citizens) can be beneficial to mission-oriented open innovation settings, where concrete solutions to today's challenges are sought.

What is expected from cities collaborating with MOSAIC?

MOSAIC's research activities will produce concrete instruments and recommendations to be used in European cities and regions willing to engage in mission-oriented approaches but also to enrich the work of Horizon Europe researchers and stakeholders more broadly.

What can MOSAIC offer to cities?

1. Capacity building: during the course of the next two years, MOSAIC partners will be providing training - particularly tailored to public sector representatives - on topics such as how to best engage citizens in mission-oriented co-creation activities, how to choose the right methodological approach when involving various stakeholders in working together towards a common challenge, or how to make citizens' ideas emerge through fair and transparent co-creation processes.
2. Tailored support: to a small number of cities, MOSAIC can provide personalised support in citizen engagement, specifically fit for the Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities mission context. Activities that MOSAIC partners can offer include a gap analysis of cities' plans or specific activities within the context of their Climate City Contract, such as the identification of missing stakeholders and opportunities, tailored suggestions on how to run citizen engagement activities, as well as support in the identification of the added value that citizen engagement can bring to identified challenges.
3. Long-term collaboration: in the next two years, MOSAIC is able to offer continuous support to cities in developing and facilitating co-creation activities aimed at the production of new products and services related to the mission.

Figure 3 - MOSAIC support for Cities & Regions

Timeline

As a first step, and following the Mission Implementation Plan, MOSAIC will provide support to selected cities in addressing citizen engagement aspects in their expression of interest for the Cities Mission. Tailored support to selected cities will be provided during the months of December 2021 and January 2022, until the deadline for submission (foreseen for the end of January 2022). Throughout 2022 and 2023, MOSAIC will provide further support to selected cities to address citizen engagement aspects in the preparation of their Climate City Contracts. Where possible, MOSAIC will select a small number of mission projects, that is concrete, identified challenges which can be addressed through co-creation, and support the process leading to the identification of shared solutions.

The MOSAIC call for interest closed on Wednesday 24 November at 23:59 CET. <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/MOSAIC-Expression-of-Interest> A full version of the survey can be found in the Annex: MOSAIC Call for Cities & Regions.

Applications

A total of 17 cities and regions from across Europe expressed interest in collaborating with the MOSAIC project. Due to the high quality of expressions of interest submitted, the MOSAIC Consortium agreed to invite all applicants to join the MOSAIC Community of Practice. This will entail supporting them through the expression of interest process for the Cities Mission, in particular in relation to citizen engagement. From this group, a number of cities will be furthermore selected to receive more tailored support for the Climate City contracting process.

- [Overview of Application – GDPR](#)
- [Overview of the Questionnaire](#)

Community of Practice

Community-building lies at the heart of many initiatives that strive to bring together individuals sharing a common sense of place, joint interests or specific social ties. It encompasses those practices and methodologies that aim at creating or enhancing a sense of community between people, focusing on what they have in common. Communities can be the place in which innovation takes place, the deployment of innovative practices, products or services being the driver for building a sense of community.

MOSAIC has embraced the concept of community-building from the beginning of the project, as a way to maximise its impact by ensuring that additional stakeholders are involved in the replication of the methodology developed throughout the project.

ERRIN, along with Stickydot, will set up a Community of Practice involving quadruple-helix stakeholders of the MOSAIC cities. This Community of Practice will be a space for discussing and sharing major project outcomes directly with the participating cities. In the first instance, activities will include **webinars** focusing on select common challenges, **presentations** of MOSAIC toolkits on methodology and impact assessment, **factsheets** on co-creation outcomes and well as specialised **policy briefs**.

Figure 4 illustrates the different levels of engagement that cities can take within the MOSAIC project. The core of the community is made up of the MOSAIC consortium partners, who will be used to support and coach the cities. The next layer is occupied by the pilot cities, which have yet to be defined but are likely to include those cities that are invited by the European Commission to develop Climate City Contracts. Despite only listing two pilots at the proposal phase, the MOSAIC consortium is looking to widen and deepen this group of pilot cities, if considered appropriate. The outer layer of engagement is dedicated to the wider MOSAIC Community of Practice, which will comprise all the cities that have submitted an interest in working on multi-stakeholder engagement in the mission context.

Figure 4 - The MOSAIC Community – levels of engagement

Peer Learning Programme

In line with the open approach of the MOSAIC consortium, to better align with the Cities Mission and further address the needs of the cities, this task has grown from what was originally planned. The Peer Learning Programme (PLP) will no longer only support four additional cities, but remain open to engagement of all of the 17 selected cities.

As explained in the previous section, MOSAIC will still look to work with a number of frontrunner or pilot cities that begin their development of Climate City Contracts in 2022. Then, through the Community of Practice, the MOSAIC partners are planning to share the results and tested methodology and tools with other cities as a peer learning programme.

Therefore, although it is possible to already define a number of broad principles for the PLP, it will be important to review both the outputs of WP2 and which cities have been successfully selected by the European Commission to join the Mission.

This section will be updated at the end of January and again in June 2022.

Peer Learning Programme Activities

The peer learning programme will consist of 4 planned peer learning workshops, one at each project meeting, where additional city representatives will be invited to join. Considering the current epidemiological situation, it is likely that these sessions will take place online and be recorded. The recordings of the peer-learning workshops will be made available on the project's website, where interested cities and regions will be able to freely access the recording and related documents.

In addition, the peer learning programme will include:

- 2 open webinars: the first of which is expected to take place in late 2022
- Bilateral exchanges between MOSAIC community members and MOSAIC pilots
- 4 peer-learning study visits, organised back-to-back with the progress meetings
- Supporting documents (such as the "MOSAIC Cookbook - a recipe for success!") will be provided.

The two webinars will be open to the public and will be organised in conjunction with the peer-learning visits. These webinars will be publicised beyond the MOSAIC community members through the project website as well as targeted outreach through social media, in order to attract a wide range of participants.

A report will be written following each peer-learning visit, focusing on the key learnings and conditions for transferability, to ensure that the outcomes feed into the sustainability of the project.

The following two sections will be updated in February and April 2022 after the Expressions of Interest have been submitted and the Mission Cities have been selected.

Supporting Cities working on the Expression of Interest

Webinar I

Webinar II

One-on-One Meetings

Peer-Learning Work Plan

Annex

MOSAIC Call for Cities & Regions

Disclaimer

The European Commission is not responsible for the content of questionnaires created using the EUSurvey service - it remains the sole responsibility of the form creator and manager. The use of EUSurvey service does not imply a recommendation or endorsement, by the European Commission, of the views expressed within them.

What can MOSAIC offer to cities?

1. Capacity building: during the course of the next two years, MOSAIC partners will be providing training - particularly tailored to public sector representatives - on topics such as how to best engage citizens in mission-oriented co-creation activities, how to choose the right methodological approach when involving various stakeholders in working together towards a common challenge, or how to make citizens' ideas emerge through fair and transparent co-creation processes.
2. Tailored support: to a small number of cities, MOSAIC can provide personalised support in citizen engagement, specifically fit for the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities missions context. Activities that MOSAIC partners can perform include for example a gap analysis of cities' plans or specific activities within the context of their Climate City Contract, such as the identification of missing stakeholders and opportunities, tailored suggestions on how to run citizen engagement activities, as well as support in the identification of the added value that citizen engagement would bring to identified challenges.
3. Long-term collaboration: in the next two years MOSAIC is able to offer continuous support to two cities in developing and facilitating co-creation activities aimed at the production of new products and services related to the Mission.

* Full Name

* Organisation

Job Title

* City and / or region represented

* Email

1. Does your city and/or region plan to apply to the European Commission's call for Expressions of Interest towards the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Mission?

- Yes
 No
 Still undecided

2. Which stakeholder groups have you involved so far in your preparatory activities towards the definition of priorities to become climate neutral within a certain set of years? (i.e. university groups, industrial lobbies, etc.)

3. At what stage of development is your Climate City Contract?

500 character(s) maximum

0 out of 500 characters used.

4. Have you involved citizens, or civil society organisations (i.e. non-for profit associations) in the preparation of your Climate City Contract (or other preparatory activities) so far? (if possible, provide a short description of how)

500 character(s) maximum

0 out of 500 characters used.

* 5. What type of support can MOSAIC offer you to assist your involvement in the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Mission at this stage?

- Help with addressing citizen engagement aspects in the Mission expression of interest
- Capacity building in citizen engagement
- Tailored support
- Other

If other, please specify

* 6. What language would you expect support activities to held?

- English
- Local language
- Both

* 7. Would you be interested in a long-term collaboration with MOSAIC?

- Yes, we would like further support related to stakeholder engagement during finalisation of our Climate City Contract
- Yes, we would like support in implementing our co-creation activities, (aimed at finding shared solutions to our identified challenges)
- Yes to both
- No
- Unsure at the moment

Submit

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Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance
Innovation through Co-creation

Boosting citizen engagement in your #CitiesMission EoI

16 December 2021

Boosting citizen engagement in your #CitiesMission EoI

16 December 2021, 10am-12pm: Part 1

11 January 2022, 2-4pm: Part 2

10:00 - 10:15 Welcome and warm-up

10:15- 10:20 MOSAIC, our expertise and what we can offer – Maria Zolotonosa, Stickydot, Brussels

10:20 - 10:45 Climate neutrality with and for citizens - Marzia Mazzonetto, Stickydot, Brussels (including Q&A)

10:45 - 11:00 How to keep citizens (fairly) engaged - Angela Simone, Bassetti Foundation, Milan (including Q&A)

11:00 - 11:05 Break

11:05 – 11:40 Three inspiring examples of citizen engagement

- Involving the private sector in co-creation processes around plastic waste and circular economy business models encouraging reuse - Mélanie Marcel, SoScience, Paris
- Co-defining needs and ideas to set the ground for co-creation in waste and water/circular economy - Marzia Mazzonetto, Stickydot
- Participatory research agenda setting supporting fair energy transition in Lombardy - Anna Pellizzone, Bassetti Foundation, Milan

11:40 - 12:00 Open discussion

Today's objectives

- Get to know each other
- Share useful experiences of multi-stakeholder engagement processes and discuss its added value
- Provide inspiring ideas of where and how it can be embedded in the EoI
- Dialogue and answer questions

Tech tips

Click "Start Video" so we can see you and "Unmute" to talk

Click "Participants" and "Chat" menu buttons

Horizon 2020
Science Society
with and for

Tested in place-based innovation ecosystems

A co-creation methodology for mission-oriented objectives

mosaic-mission.eu

With cities active in the Horizon Europe Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities

Develop a mutual learning process through the MOSAIC community of practice

mosaic-mission.eu

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MOSAIC support to Cities/regions

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Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

Climate neutrality with and for citizens

Marzia Mazzonetto, Stickydot

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MULTI-STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT IN THE #CITIESMISSION

Behavioural change, modal shifts, local community level, regulatory, financial incentives and fiscal instruments, information/awareness raising, voluntary measures, etc.

Getting citizens on board through showcasing (potential and far away) tangible benefits for them (i.e. better air quality, more jobs, more green spaces etc.) has only limited impact.

➔ building and implementing a future vision together with them...

IN PARTICULAR, CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT (CE) REPRESENTS AN OPPORTUNITY TO...

- Boost creativity (more ideas, better innovation)
- Prepare for potential adverse impacts by engaging with (and learning from) citizens
- Harness the trust building potential of CE by detailing co-benefits at an early stage of the process
- Leave no one behind through wide inclusion (“we’re in it together”)
- Implement transparent, democratic processes

HOW?

CO-DESIGN

TYPE OF ACTIVITIES

R&I agenda setting, surveys, consensus conferences, citizen assemblies, participatory budgeting, scenario building, forum programmes (US), in-depth focus groups, etc.

WHO IS INVOLVED

National, regional or local governments; Funding agencies; CSOs; Research institutions; Facilitators.

WHAT YOU GET

- Legitimisation of key policy orientations (rarely disruptive)
- Prioritising key issues
- Commitment (on both side)
- But also... research and business ideas, etc.

SCALE AND TIMELINE

Regionally or nationally: setting broader priorities (i.e. S3, R&I strategic plans, national goals, SDGs).
(Locally: place-based missions).
Typically 2 to 6 months processes (or longer).

Co-design works at its best when it becomes a tool to regularly collect both broad and challenge specific **orientation knowledge** to make sure that **democratically legitimate priorities** are being tackled.

CO-CREATION

TYPE OF ACTIVITIES

Design thinking, participatory workshops, collaborative making, DIY science, etc.

WHAT YOU GET

- Tangible solutions to missions
- Constructive citizen engagement in innovation ecosystems

WHO IS INVOLVED

4-Helix: Companies, citizens or CSOs, research organisations, public agencies.

Typically Makerspaces & Living Labs, but it's even better when the co-creation takes in place where R&I are already happening (i.e. industrial or territorial settings).

SCALE AND TIMELINE

Mostly local or regional: place-based mission projects.

Adaptability and replicability.

1 week to 3 months or more (depending on how defined the problem is).

AN EXAMPLE: CITIZEN SCIENCE

Data collection and beyond.

It can be used for both co-design and co-creation.

But if not done with purpose, it can lead to...

AWARENESS RAISING – THE POWER OF CULTURE

TYPE OF ACTIVITIES

science festivals, [art&science](#), science shows, science exhibitions, theatre shows, stands at shopping centres, influencers, informal science education, life-long learning, etc.

WHAT YOU GET

- informed citizens (who still make their own choices)
- making missions understood (possibly in a creative way)
- tackling mis-information

WHO IS INVOLVED

science and natural museums, local funding agencies (science festivals), research centres (open days, researchers nights, etc.), media including social media (!!!)

SCALE AND TIMELINE

Always
At all levels

Citizens could be involved in the **co-design of communication priorities** and in the **co-creation of communication strategies & ideas**.

WHAT ARE WE FOCUSING ON TODAY

We are going to see today examples of co-design and co-creation processes involving multiple stakeholders, which have led to meaningful changes (meaningful = with added value for all those involved).

We have also listened to you (thank you for filling the questionnaire) - so first let's have a look at some overall reflections on how to get citizens on board and keep them motivated to take part.

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Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance
Innovation through Co-creation

How to keep citizens (fairly) engaged

Angela Simone
Bassetti Foundation

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CITIZENS ARE NOT INTERESTED IN SUCH TOPICS.

Eurobarometer «Climate action and Environment», 2021

CITIZENS ARE NOT INTERESTED IN SUCH TOPICS.

GENERATION GRETA

CITIZENS ARE NOT INTERESTED IN SUCH TOPICS.

GILETS JAUNES

**CITIZENS CANNOT UNDERSTAND/DECIDE
ON/CONTRIBUTE TO INNOVATION SINCE THEY DON'T
HAVE TECHNICAL COMPETENCES.**

- (Sound) Participation processes entail also receiving (neutral and reliable) information
- Lay knowledge as further source for place-based innovations

PARTICIPATORY PROCESSES. OPEN AND CLOSED CALLS

CO-DESIGN AND DELIBERATION. BEYOND THE OPEN CALL

SHARED DECISIONS --> DEMOCRATIC CHOICES □ REPRESENTATIVENESS OF THE POPULATION INVOLVED

Everyone should have an equal opportunity to be selected as a participant

STRENGTHS

- **INCLUSIVITY:** bringing in typically excluded categories like youth, the disadvantaged, women, or other minorities into public policy and decision making.
- **CORRUPTION PREVENTION:** by ensuring that groups and individuals with money and power cannot have undue influence on a public decision

HOW

Random sampling - representative selection based on stratification by demographics to ensure the group broadly matches the demographic profile of the community against at least age; geography, and socioeconomic factors, and sometimes by attitudinal criteria (depending on the context)

-> CIVIC LOTTERY (TWO-STAGE/DOUBLE SAMPLING)

FAIR CO-DESIGN PROCESS. KEYWORDS

INTEGRITY HIGH-QUALITY PROCESS WITH PROFESSIONALS (FOR DESIGN, FACILITATION, ETC)

FEASIBILITY: CAREFULLY CONSIDER TIME AND PROCEDURES CONSTRAINTS. AND SUFFICIENT TIME TO ANALYZE AND INCLUDE CITIZENS' RECOMMENDATIONS IN THE POLICYMAKING PROCESS

ACTIONABILITY: THE PROCESS SHOULD ENABLE THE EMERSON OF RECOMMENDATIONS THAT POLICYMAKERS CAN ACTUALLY USE

FAIR CO-DESIGN PROCESS, FAIR REWARD

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Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance
Innovation through Co-creation

SoScience: Involving the private sector in co-creation processes around plastic waste and circular economy business models encouraging reuse

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Co-creation example: An open innovation program to end plastic waste

SoScience
DRIVING RESPONSIBLE INNOVATION

Objective Expand efforts beyond the development of 100% recycled and recyclable packaging to develop solutions that re-imagine packaging from sources

to end-of-life, with the potential for delivering positive environmental and social impact.

perrier Why and how to involve the private sector?

- Neutrality roadmaps to reach
- Finding tomorrow's BM and products
- Access support & incentives
- Interconnected issues

Co-create solutions with all stakeholders

Creating motivation:

- make participation meaningful (designing AND implementation of solutions)
- do not differentiate experts (engage all stakeholders at once)
- make sure everyone that counts is there

Sustain motivation:

- Plan ahead the following steps
- Provide support for the implementation

In the EoI: policy instruments: "Third party financing, Public Private Partnerships" "Voluntary agreements with stakeholders" "Regulations" "Grants and subsidies"

stakeholders involved: "National government; Financial institutions" "Regional government" "Neighboring local/regional government" "NGOs and associations" "Academia / Research & Innovation (R&I) institutions" "Utilities" "Private sector" "Citizen and communities"

Key results - Key success factors

Flexikeg

An "ecolaboration" to deliver water and other beverages, in an innovative and re-usable flexible keg with the aim to reduce plastic waste and carbon emission

In the EoI, Collaboration with the private sector

- "Public Private Partnerships for climate neutral infrastructure and services"
- "Promoting start-ups and green jobs creation"
- "Research & Innovation, new technologies"
- "Crowdfunding from companies and SMEs in climate neutral infrastructure and services"

Sous les fraises

Urban agrifarms on rooftops in Paris and Ile-De-France.

Collaborative project between Sous les fraises and the Research Performing Organization INRAE issued from the program The Future Of Urban Agriculture.

In the EoI, Citizen engagement

- "Participatory urban planning"
- "Ad-hoc co-creation engagement practices"

mosaic
Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance
Innovation through Co-creation

**Co-defining needs and ideas to
set the ground for co-creation in
waste and water/circular
economy**

Marzia Mazzonetto, Stickydot

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101003262 - H2020-SwafW-2019-2020 / H2020-SwafW-2020-1

TWO EXAMPLES OF...

- Co-design priorities / make ideas for potential co-creation solutions emerge
- Involving citizens in addressing concrete challenges: better waste management (towards a zero-waste society) and reducing bottled water consumption
- Similar methodological approach: tailored focus groups

mosaic

Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance
Innovation through Co-creation

**Participatory research agenda
setting supporting fair energy
transition in Lombardy**

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**STICKY
DOT**

ERRIN
European Regions
Research and Innovation Network

FB
Fondazione Gianna Saccetti
for Responsibility in Innovation

soScience
DRIVING RESPONSIBLE INNOVATION

**Université
Gustave Eiffel**

WASTE MANAGEMENT

WASTE MANAGEMENT

WATER CONSUMPTION

AQUASENS

AQUASENS EST UN CAPTEUR D'EAU ACTUELLEMENT EN DÉVELOPPEMENT.

C'EST UN OUTIL **ACCESSIBLE** QUI PERMET AUX UTILISATEURS DE DÉTERMINER LA QUALITÉ DE L'EAU AU

POINT D'INTERVENTION

TOUT LE MONDE PEUT L'UTILISER

PAS BESOIN DE FORMATION SPÉCIFIQUE

COMMENT FONCTIONNE LE CAPTEUR?

DU PAPIER ATTIRE L'EAU

SI DE LA COULEUR ROUGE EST ÉMISE, NE PAS BOIRE!

WATER CONSUMPTION

KEY OUTCOMES

People's lack of commitment is often seen as not caring about/not knowing about. In reality, most people face strong dilemmas between environmental and personal concerns when dealing with environmentally relevant issues.

The broad concept of "incentives": for the community, less so individual ones.

Research and innovations are rarely focused on the household level (issues are handled somewhere else, people are expected to contribute).

People want to have an active role in the uptake of the potential solutions (i.e. citizen labels).

Ideas for next steps...

Co-design experience: fair energy transition for all in Lombardy region

TRANSFORM in Lombardy:

Engaging Lombardy population in the definition of the social needs at the basis of the regional research and innovation strategies.

Deliberative workshop:

Providing Lombardy Region with recommendations from citizens towards a fair energy transition for all

TRANSFORM
LOMBARDY

Deliberative online workshop

Fair energy transition for all

- The topic: fair energy transition for all
- Design, conduction and analysis: Giannino Bassetti Foundation
- Support of an external agency (for conduction and recruitment)
- The participants: 18 Lombardy citizens (calibrated by gender, age, province of residence)
- When: May 2021
- Duration: 8 hours on Saturday
- The output: recommendations for Lombardy Region R&I strategies

Deliberative workshop

Key stages

Regione Lombardia | Open innovation

IL PROGETTO

Uno sviluppo del territorio inclusivo, trasparente e responsabile: con questa ambizione nasce TRANSFORM, il progetto finanziato dalla Commissione Europea che mira a coinvolgere i cittadini nelle decisioni su ricerca e innovazione a livello regionale.

SCOPRI DI PIÙ

IN LOMBARDIA

TRANSFORM aiuta i governi regionali a integrare la Responsible Research and Innovation nelle loro pratiche: grazie al progetto, Regione Lombardia ha coinvolto i cittadini nella definizione dei bisogni di ricerca e innovazione del territorio e delle persone che lo abitano.

SCOPRI DI PIÙ

IL PERCORSO PARTECIPATIVO

In Lombardia, un campione rappresentativo della popolazione è stato chiamato a rispondere a un questionario e a partecipare a un workshop deliberativo. I cittadini hanno espresso le loro opinioni in modo concreto e hanno raccontato quali sono le loro priorità in termini di ricerca e innovazione.

SCOPRI DI PIÙ

Public communication and outreach

- Webpage on the Lombardy Region platform Open Innovation
- Internal presentation to other regional Directorates
- Online webinar with Lombardy Technological Cluster (group of stakeholders)
- Public event

Key practical details

For a fair, effective and transparent process

The deliberative wave

OECD resources

- [Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions: Catching the Deliberative Wave report \(2020\)](#)
- [Evaluation Guidelines for Representative Deliberative Processes \(2021\)](#)
- [OECD databases of Representative Deliberative Processes and Institutions \(2021\)](#)

● **Values-driven dilemmas**

● **Complex problems that require trade-offs**

● **Long-term issues that go beyond the short-term incentives of electoral cycles**

Climate assemblies

Proliferation of climate assemblies (UK, France, Ireland, Scotland, Germany, Finland, Denmark...)

KNOCA network: Knowledge Network on Climate Assemblies

Etc.

We are going to see each other in 2022

11 January 2022 14:00-16:00 CET

On zoom register here: <https://bit.ly/3sipSf8>

mosaic

Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance
Innovation through Co-creation

www.mosaic.eu

@mosaic_eu

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Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

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